

COURSE MODULE IN PURPOSIVE COMMUNICATION FOR FRESHMEN COLLEGE STUDENTS

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Course Module in Purposive Communication for Freshmen College Students

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Abstract

This study attempted to develop and evaluate a course module in Purposive Communication for freshmen college students in National University Fairview during the school year 2023 - 2024. Specifically, it identified the lessons that could be developed into a course module based on the course syllabus, compared the evaluation of instructors and expert respondents on the developed module based on the course learning outcomes (CLOs), lesson content, processing tasks/questions and assessment tasks, and recognized the comments and suggestions of evaluators to improve the module. The descriptive type of research was utilized to gather and evaluate data from the two groups of respondents which include fifteen (15) Purposive Communication instructors with degrees in Language, English, Curriculum Development or equivalent and with aligned MA units, and fifteen (15) expert respondents with at least master's degree in Language, English, Curriculum Development or equivalent. Furthermore, weighted means and independent sample t-test were utilized to determine the magnitude of the evaluation and to identify the significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents. Evaluations and analyses of data reveal that the lessons that were developed into a Purposive Communication course module based on the course syllabus are: a) Communication processes, principles, and ethics, b) Communication and globalization, c) Local and global communication in multicultural settings d) Varieties and registers of spoken and written language, e) Evaluating messages and/or images of different types of texts reflecting different cultures, f) Communication aids and strategies using tools of technology, g) Communication for various purposes, and h) Communication for academic purposes. In addition, instructors and expert respondents evaluated the course module in terms of the course learning outcomes, lesson content, processing tasks/questions and assessment tasks with grand weighted mean ratings of 3.92 and 3.81, respectively, both interpreted as Very Strongly Agree (VSA). Furthermore, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents in terms of the aforementioned criteria with p-values of 0.05, 0.14, 0.20, and 0.29, respectively, which are all not less than the 5% level of significance. There are also some comments and suggestions on how to improve the developed course module in Purposive Communication.

Keywords: *Purposive Communication, course module, college students*

Introduction

The proposed General Education (GE) curriculum as laid down by CHED in 2013 contains the eight (8) GE subjects which are taught at present – Understanding the Self, The Contemporary World, Art Appreciation, Ethics, Readings in Philippine History, Mathematics in the Modern World, Science, Technology and Society, and Purposive Communication (Pazzibugan, 2013).

Purposive Communication focuses primarily in the different forms of communication to be practiced, in dealing with different target audiences in multicultural settings (Mehta, 2023). According to CHED Memorandum Order No, 20 s. 2013,

Purposive Communication is about writing, speaking, and presenting to different audiences and for various purposes. (CMO 20 s. 2013). It is a three-unit course that develops students' communicative competence and enhances their cultural and intercultural awareness through multimodal tasks that provide them opportunities for communicating effectively and appropriately to a multicultural audience in a local or global context. It equips students with tools for critical evaluation of a variety of texts and focuses on the power of language and the impact of images to emphasize the importance of conveying messages responsibly. The knowledge, skills, and insights that students gain from this course may be used in their other academic endeavors, their chosen disciplines, and their future careers as they compose and produce relevant oral, written, audio-visual, and/or web-based output for various purposes.

Therefore, it is essential for college students to develop a level of cultural and intercultural awareness to place themselves in a position that enables them to communicate appropriately, without being discriminating or derogatory. Moreover, the course would assist them to develop skills in communicating for both the academic and professional settings. The Purposive Communication curriculum promotes these skills.

The development of the Purposive Communication course module and the evaluation of its content will offer a supplementary or alternative process making sure that students receive the quality teaching materials in this aspect of general education. The module will also promote a student-friendly instructional process so that learners may find it positioned between self-learning and teacher-guided.

The aim of this modular development is to develop a Purposive Communication module that would be suitable for a 12-week period without compromising quality education. Furthermore, National University offers an institutional course called Advanced Communication which focuses on communication in the workplace, allowing the logical modification of CHED's Purposive

Communication syllabus through substituting the topic, Communication for Work Purposes, with a more focused discussion on Communication for Academic Purposes. In addition, the researcher would want to employ a research-natured assessment to promote the immersion of learners to the different aspects of language and communication in real-life scenarios in terms of language studies. According to Zarah (2022), research is essential to succeeding not only in the academe, but also to many professions. Its main purpose is to discover ideas, study concepts, gather evidence for theories, explore and investigate implications, and contribute to the existing body of knowledge. Goubert (2018) emphasizes the importance of researches in communication including raising public awareness and promoting public engagement.

DepEd claimed that one factor that determines the kind of education being offered by schools is the kind of learning resources they are utilizing. Quality learning resources equip teachers to provide better assistance and guidance to learners in “mastering the skills, knowledge, and experiences that will support learners in school and in life.” In line with this, and in a regular face-to-face set-up, textbooks or print materials are the primarily learning resources used by teachers and learners to attain the objectives of the curriculum (Hernando-Malipot, 2021).

Research Questions

This study attempted to develop and evaluate module on Purposive Communication for use of freshmen college students at the National University-Fairview during the school year, 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lessons in Purposive Communication that could be developed into a course module based on the course syllabus?
2. How do instructor and expert respondents evaluate the developed course module in Purposive Communication for college students in terms of the following parts:
 - 2.1. Course Learning Outcomes
 - 2.2. Lesson Content
 - 2.3. Processing Questions/Tasks
 - 2.4. Assessment Tasks
3. Is there a significant difference between the evaluations of the instructor and expert respondents on the developed course module based on the aforementioned parts?
4. What are the comments and suggestions of instructor and expert respondents in order to improve the Purposive Communication course module?

Literature Review

According to Wiley (2017), the term module refers to different things to different people. For a modular course design, however, module refers to organizational units that one uses to organize the content or components of a course. It may contain discussions, live sessions, learning objectives, video lectures, readings, lessons and assessment tasks. Wiley also added that a modular approach to a course design puts a course into an organized and logical way that emphasizes the objectives of the course and facilitates the essential knowledge and skills that learners should apply. Furthermore, Wiley presents key ideas on how to effectively organize course content through modules which includes identifying key topic areas, labeling modules clearly and consistently, and creating modules of consistent structure.

Johnson (2020) defined the term module as synonymous to online lessons or units. The content of these said online course modules typically include activities organized to clearly guide the students to achieve learning goals and objectives. Johnson also pointed out that before planning for a modular structure, an instructor must note that people disregard boring content and the human brain processes things on a sequential manner especially if multi-tasking is required. Therefore, multi-tasking becomes a common response to boring experiences, compromising the attention required to accomplish particular tasks as originally planned. In this technological era, the whole internet is just one click away, and therefore encourages multi-tasking which results to low attention and eventually, low learning. Johnson highlighted how module design, therefore, becomes essential. An instructor have control over most of the elements in a learners' learning experience which include the pedagogy on lectures, the arrangement of content and activities, the consultation period and the appropriateness of assessments, the nature of learning experiences, and the movement of experiences in terms of the learners' cognitive ability levels.

For Kalantzis and Cope (2023), a learning module is designed and developed unit of work by course instructors using Learning by Design framework. This framework promotes how learners are guided and supported, and therefore, is the basis for modular designs. A learning module using this framework consists of the learning focus which is the subject/topics to be studied and discussed including prior knowledge, knowledge of objectives which are the goals that learners must be able to achieve, knowledge processes or the learning activities designed and developed, knowledge outcomes or the learning activities that students should accomplish to assess their understanding of the concepts, and learning pathways. These learning modules created using the framework may be published and shared with colleagues.

Toohey as cited by Burge (2019) claims that teachers in higher education has control over the curriculum, which gives them advantage over teachers in other branches of education. This includes their liberty on creativity and power in teaching which all lies in curriculum

design. Their choice of materials and ideas become the central focus of study and learner experiences lies in their notion of achievement and assessment. She also added that good course design multiplies the power of good teacher-student interactions by a large number.

Burge suggests that designing a module is a great responsibility and therefore she shares key things to achieve such endeavor. This includes being clear about the purpose of the module and aspirations for the student learners and to communicate these to them, making sure that the module is aligned constructively as demonstrated by teaching and assessment aligning with the intended outcomes, and considering the course in context (department, institution, or sector).

Johnson (2020) avers that good modules include knowledge consumption through essential skills such as reading, listening and viewing. These provide opportunities for students to process the concept they have learned. This processing can be in the form of a quiz, application activity, discussions or reflections. Instructors often expect learners to demonstrate their acquired knowledge or skills in different forms of assessments which may include different kinds of tests, and some of the tasks may look the same with the processing or enabling activities. He also added that structuring or organizing a module must be guided by the nature of activities whether these are synchronous or asynchronous. In an online teaching modality a learning path for students to follow requires a clear, predictable, well-marked module structure. Johnson also claims that the same series of activities with no variation day after day, module after module, will bore both students and instructors. Therefore, sticking to the modular structure while varying the activities once in a while, is a good approach.

Learning goals as stated by McKay (2020) have a “multicultural” requirement in a given general education plan considering marginalized groups – factors on the marginalization and the cultural study of these groups. In conclusion, one should consider the rearrangement of class into modules and the learning goals that could be established for them.

Mehta (2023) claims that Purposive Communication focuses primarily in the different forms of communication to be practices in dealing with different target audiences in a multicultural setting. This is the main mode of communication used in different organizations and includes speaking, writing and presenting using various channels. Purposive communication explores the idea of communication having to achieve different sets of objectives. Ergo, it encourages the communicator to intentionally use the appropriate forms of communication to be executed in global or multicultural settings.

Mikell (2020) mentions that in an online set up, faculty members with little experience may struggle to develop and administer the content to impart expertise and facilitate student learning and retention. Therefore, instructors must carefully deliberate how to carry out particular courses to ensure that learners will meet or even exceed course outcomes. Mikell offered tips to start designing and structuring modules in an online course. This includes knowing the learning management system (LMS) and resources. Institutional technical assistance is also recommended for course design support. Another principle is course planning by carefully knowing course competencies and course outcomes. When competencies are established and organized, they shall be divided into categories with logical sequence to maximize student learning. The principle of backward design is an effective tool to carry out this endeavor through considering what students should know and be able to do as a result of taking the course with the end in mind.

In addition, Mikell also strongly suggests that the learning module should contain the objectives relevant to expected student outcomes, which should be clear, concise and contain measurable criteria. Each module should include the course content, topics, assignments and tasks, resources and appropriate assessment focused on themes and level of learners. For modular activities, Mikell suggests that each module can begin with a checklist of items for completion inclusive of due dates. They should also be aligned to its measurable learning objectives, with resources and activities, organized and easy-to-follow, clear and concise directions and applicable assessments aligned to the objectives.

According to Hernando-Malipot (2021) DepEd said that one factor that determines the kind of education being offered by schools is the kind of learning resources they are utilizing. Therefore, if an institution aims for quality education to be offered to students, then it is crucial to monitor or to evaluate the quality of learning resources being provided to learners and teachers. DepEd also added that quality learning resources equip teachers to provide better assistance and guidance to learners in “mastering the skills, knowledge, and experiences that will support learners in school and in life.” In line with this, and in a regular face-to-face set-up, textbooks or print materials are the primarily learning resources used by teachers and learners to attain the objectives of the curriculum.

The University of Minnesota Teaching Support (2020) published a book discussing designing a course module. The university suggests that instructors would want to provide a variety of instructional materials, tasks and assessments to elevate student engagement. These materials may range from videos, journals, articles, podcasts events websites, practice quizzes, problem-solving, group works, discussions and projects. Accessibility to chosen materials is also one of the important factors. In addition, estimating the appropriate amount of work is equally important. UMN claims that instructors and content experts often underestimate the time needed to complete course content and task completion. However, it is not possible to provide an exact time, so it should be advised to students that what the module offers are guidelines on how they should spend their time rather than a limit. This caters to the issue on students’ rate of learning. Overall, UMN recommends that content experts would want to make sure that instructors offer an appropriate amount of work per week for students to achieve the learning outcomes in the developed course modules.

Fairbanks (2021) from University of Phoenix discussed the five (5) educational learning theories and how to apply them. Behaviorism Learning Theory by Watson proposes that observable stimulus-response behaviors can be studied in a systematic and observable

manner. This means that learners may learn on a system of routines or “drills” and feedbacks affect the way they receive learning and progress on it. Cognitivism Learning Theory relies on both external and internal factors which mean that the acquisition of knowledge is processed by the learner which is an information-processor. Constructivism Theory as pioneered by Piaget states that the learners based their understanding on previous experiences to construct a new understanding. In education, learners construct meaning through active engagement with the world such as real-life application of concepts. The other two (2) theories are Humanism and Connectivism Theory which state that curriculum should focus on self-actualization and remediating knowledge gaps, respectively.

Harrapa (2022) explained that the bases for the learning system of Outcomes-Based Education (OBE) are the desired outcomes. The curriculum is designed with the end in mind, hence the course content, tasks and assessments are developed based on the desired outcomes. OBE has a number of benefits in the learning process which include having a clear purpose, being goal-oriented, having practical emphases and being a flexible approach. Its principles include having a ‘design down’ approach, putting students first by considering their rate and level of learning, students achieve high standards, and assessments are key in measuring learning outcomes. Though OBE faces criticisms such as missing the nuance, the kind of assessments used and the flexibility it gives is too much, with an expertly defined program with proper defined outcomes and assessment strategy, the result can be a good experience for learners.

The Philippine Daily Inquirer (2013) reported about CHED laying down new General Education (GE) courses for colleges and universities with the alignment to the K-12 program, the new curriculum will be taken up for only one (1) year instead of the two-year practice since most of these GE courses are already taken up during the senior high school years. This proposed GE curriculum contains the eight (8) GE subjects which are being taught at present – Understanding the Self, The Contemporary World, Art Appreciation, Ethics, Readings in Philippine History, Mathematics in the Modern World, Science, Technology and Society, and Purposive Communication (Pazzibugan, 2013).

Nazario (2020) stated that the Alliance of Concerned Teachers Philippines said that problems on Self-Learning Modules (SLM) of the Department of Education remain. ACT clarified that SLMs are inadequate and untimely and “delays learners’ access to education” and affects the quality of learning. As a response, it is recommended that DepEd should release its operational plan and status reports with timeline and budget for the production and distribution of SLMs. ACT also suggested that DepEd considers the use of available textbooks pending the provision of materials despite its inadequacy and limitations.

According to Zarah (2022), research is essential to succeeding not only in the academe, but also to many professions. Its main purpose is to discover ideas, study concepts, gather evidence for theories, explore and investigate implications, and contribute to the existing body of knowledge. Research on language studies is therefore an effective tool to immerse learners into the evolution of the different aspects of communication and languages.

Goubert (2018) emphasizes the importance of researches in communication including raising public awareness and promoting public engagement. With the essential information from gathered data, comprehensive decisions can be made from a governmental to an individual level.

Methodology

Respondents

Evaluation of module included selecting instructors and experts in the field. This comprised of 15 licensed teachers majoring in Language, English, Filipino and Communication or equivalent with aligned MA units, learning module developers, and 15 experts with master’s degree in Language, English, Filipino, Communication and Curriculum Development or equivalent. They were given the validated evaluation tool with questionnaire items adapted from Evaluation of a Proposed Set of Modules in Principles and Methods of Teaching by Macarandang (2009) and based on Chapter 2: Adapting Courses in Developing Materials in Language Teaching by Brian Tomlinson presented in 2022 with the following criteria: 1) course learning outcomes (CLO), 2) lesson content, 3) processing questions/tasks, and 4) assessment tasks.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents in the Development and Evaluation of Course Module in Purposive Communication

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Number of Respondents</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Instructors	15	50%
Experts	15	50%
Total	30	100%

Instruments

Modular development included gathering information to accumulate the prescribed lessons and competencies set by the learning objectives as per CHED (CMO No. 20 S. 2013) as reflected in the course syllabus. The process involved organizing information into specific parts namely the lessons, the tasks, and the appropriate assessments to carry out the teaching-learning processes of the instructor-guided Purposive Communication course module.

For modular evaluation, the survey questionnaire items were adapted from Evaluation of a Proposed Set of Modules in Principles and Methods of Teaching by Macarandang (2009) and based on Chapter 2: Adapting Courses in Developing Materials in Language

Teaching by Brian Tomlinson presented in 2022 was utilized to identify and analyze the score evaluations of Purposive Communication instructors and expert respondents on the developed module. The evaluation tool was subjected for content validity and reliability test through pilot testing. The test of reliability showed a coefficient of 0.969 using Cronbach's Alpha based on Standardized Items as shown in Appendix B. This presents an evidence of internal consistency of the research instrument. Furthermore, the variables to be considered were the course learning outcomes, lesson content, processing questions/tasks and assessment tasks.

Procedure

Intensive information was gathered to identify the gaps, the legal basis, the methodology, theories and variables needed to execute the study. The guidance of experts to critique and advise the researcher was needed to carry out the research proposal. Related literature and studies were gathered to support the feasibility of the paper and to identify theoretical foundations on where the paper should focus on.

Content of the proposed course module was executed based on the institutionalized course syllabus aligned to the learning objectives set by CHED (CMO No. 20 S. 2013). An evaluation tool for the developed Purposive Communication course module was established through content validity and reliability tests through pilot testing. After the components were organized and the evaluation tool prepared, a letter of permission was sent to the academic director and the dean of the institution's School of Arts and Sciences to make the data gathering official. The developed module was then presented to the instructors and expert respondents for evaluation. The privacy and anonymity, willingness to participate on the basis of informed consent, and data privacy of the respondents were given attention for ethical considerations.

The evaluation process made use of the validated evaluation tool with questionnaire items adapted from Evaluation of a Proposed Set of Modules in Principles and Methods of Teaching by Macarandang (2009) and based on Chapter 2: Adapting Courses in Developing Materials in Language Teaching by Brian Tomlinson presented in 2022, with the scoring sheets administered by the researcher through Google Forms. The retrieval of the scoring sheets took place, analyzing the significant difference of the scores between the two (2) groups of respondents, and the disposal was made immediately after the statistical treatment. Comments and suggestions were gathered from the respondents to thematically identify the recommendations to further improve the course module.

Afterwards, the paper was subjected to an online plagiarism checker to identify the revisions needed for the research paper.

Ethical Considerations

The developed module was presented to the qualified instructors and expert respondents for evaluation. The privacy and anonymity, willingness to participate on the basis of informed consent, and data privacy of the respondents were given attention for ethical considerations.

Results and Discussion

Lessons in Purposive Communication Developed into Course Module Based on the Institutional Course Syllabus Aligned with CHED Memorandum Order No. 20 s. 2013

Table 2 presents the lessons in Purposive Communication that was developed into a course module based on the institutional course syllabus aligned with CHED Memorandum Order No. 20 s. 2013.

The table shows the list of lessons that was developed into Purposive Communication course module for freshmen college students with the corresponding number of hours required to achieve the objectives of the specific lesson/s. The Purposive Communication curriculum for this school year, 2023 – 2024 was issued by the Commission on Higher Education in line with the CHED Memorandum Order No. 20 s. 2013.

The lessons in the course syllabus were recommended by experts and commissioners from the Commission on Higher Education and the Purposive Communication course module was carefully evaluated and validated by professionals from the different institutions in terms of its course learning outcomes, lesson content, processing tasks/questions, and assessment tasks.

Table 2. Lessons Developed into a Course Module in Purposive Communication Based on the Course Syllabus

<i>Lessons</i>	<i>Expected Number of Hours</i>
1. Communication processes, principles and ethics	2 hours (Week 2)
2. Communication and globalization	2 hours (Week 2)
3. Local and global communication in multicultural settings	1 hour (Week 3)
4. Varieties and registers of spoken language	1 hour (Week 3)
5. Evaluating messages and/or images of different types of texts reflecting different cultures	2 hours (Week 3)
6. Communication aids and strategies using tools of technology	4 hours (Week 4)
7. Communication for various purposes	12 hours (Week 5-6)
8. Communication for academic purposes	28 hours (Week 7-13)

Number of Hours: 4 hours every week for 13.5 weeks, 2 hours for midterm and final examinations

Table 2 shows that the course syllabus includes the following lessons: Communication, processes, principles and ethics, Communication and Local and global communication in multicultural settings, Varieties and registers of spoken language, Evaluation messages and/or images of different types of texts reflecting different cultures, Communication aids and strategies using tools of technology, Communication for various purposes and Communication for academic purposes. This implies that a module could be developed based on the course syllabus aligned with CMO No. 20 s 2013 curriculum guide suited for a trimester set-up.

Evaluation of the Instructors and Expert Respondents on the Developed Course Module in Purposive Communication

Tables 3 to 6 present the evaluations of the course instructors and expert respondents on the developed Purposive Communication course module in terms of course learning outcomes, lesson content, processing tasks/questions, and assessment tasks. Table 7 presents the summary.

Course Learning Outcomes. Table 3 shows the evaluation of the course instructors and the expert respondents on the developed Purposive Communication course module in terms of the course learning outcomes.

Table 3. Evaluation on the Developed Purposive Communication Course Module in Terms of the Course Learning Outcomes

<i>Course Learning Outcomes</i>	<i>Instructors</i>		<i>Experts</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>
<i>The course learning outcomes...</i>				
1. for each lesson are attainable with the time allotment.	3.87	VSA	3.53	VSA
2. for each lesson are realistic.	3.87	VSA	3.60	VSA
3. for each lesson are measurable.	3.93	VSA	3.67	VSA
4. are organized from easy to difficult.	3.87	VSA	3.67	VSA
5. are according to the prescribed CHED curriculum.	4.00	VSA	3.80	VSA
	Mean	3.91 VSA	3.65	VSA
	Overall Average	3.78		VSA

Legend: *M* (Mean); *VI* (Verbal Interpretation); 3.26-4.00 VSA (Very Strongly Agree); 2.51-3.25 (Strongly Agree); 1.76-2.50 (Agree); 1.00-1.75 (Disagree)

As presented in Table 3, the evaluation of the developed course module in terms of the course learning outcomes were evaluated by instructors and expert respondents mean ratings of 3.91 and 3.65, respectively, verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree (VSA). The overall average is 3.78 which is verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree (VSA).

The data revealed that both instructors and experts find the developed course module in terms of the course learning outcomes as very highly acceptable. This implies that for each given lesson, the course learning outcomes (CLOs) are attainable with the time allotment, realistic, measurable, organized from easy to difficult and are according to the prescribed CHED curriculum.

As stated by Mikell (2020), the learning module should contain the objectives relevant to expected student outcomes, which should be clear, concise and contain measurable criteria. In addition, when competencies are established and organized, they shall be divided into categories with logical sequence to maximize student learning. The principle of backward design is an effective tool to carry out this endeavor through considering what students should know and be able to do as a result of taking the course with the end in mind. This principle greatly helped with the arrangement of weekly objectives to achieve carry out the final output of a language or communication research.

Lesson Content. Table 4 presents the evaluation of the instructor and expert respondents on the Purposive Communication course module according to the lesson content.

As presented in Table 4, the evaluation of the developed course module in terms of the lesson content were evaluated by instructors and expert respondents with mean ratings of 3.91 and 3.73, respectively, verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree (VSA), which resulted to an overall average mean of 3.82 with verbal interpretation of Very Strongly Agree (VSA).

Table 4. Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Purposive Communication Course Module in terms of Lesson Content

<i>Lesson Content</i>	<i>Instructors</i>		<i>Experts</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>
<i>The lesson content...</i>				
1. introduces the most important aspects of what is being taught.	4.00	VSA	3.67	VSA
2. has well-expressed ideas, concepts and points.	3.87	VSA	3.73	VSA
3. leads to the attainment of the objectives of the course.	3.93	VSA	3.73	VSA
4. presents adequate and accurate information.	3.80	VSA	3.73	VSA
5. illustrates examples that are current, accurate and defensible.	3.93	VSA	3.80	VSA
	Mean	3.91 VSA	3.73	VSA
	Overall Average	3.82		VSA

Legend: *M* (Mean); *VI* (Verbal Interpretation); 3.26-4.00 VSA (Very Strongly Agree); 2.51-3.25 (Strongly Agree); 1.76-2.50 (Agree); 1.00-1.75 (Disagree)

The data revealed that both instructors and experts are very satisfied the developed course module in terms of the lesson content. This signifies that the content introduces the most important aspects, has well-expressed ideas, concepts and points, leads to the attainment

of the objectives, presents adequate and accurate information and has current, accurate and defensible examples.

Wiley (2017) presents key ideas on how to effectively organize course content through modules which includes identifying key topic areas, labeling modules clearly and consistently, and creating modules of consistent structure. In addition, Johnson (2020) emphasized that an instructor must note that people disregard boring content and the human brain processes things on a sequential manner especially if multi-tasking is required. Harrapa (2022) stated that the curriculum should be designed with the end in mind, hence the course content, tasks and assessments are developed based on the desired outcomes.

Processing Tasks/Questions. Table 5 presents the evaluation of the course instructors and expert respondents on the developed Purposive Communication course module according to its processing task/questions.

As presented in Table 5, the evaluation of the developed course module in terms of the lesson content were evaluated by instructors and expert respondents with mean ratings of 3.87 and 3.73, respectively, verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree (VSA), which resulted to an overall average mean of 3.80 with verbal interpretation of Very Strongly Agree (VSA).

Table 5. *Evaluation on the Developed Purposive Communication Course Module in terms of Processing Tasks/Questions*

<i>Processing Tasks/Questions</i> <i>The processing tasks/questions...</i>	<i>Instructors</i>		<i>Experts</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. are presented at a pace that allows for reflection and review.	3.73	VSA	3.67	VSA
2. adequately provide supplementary activities/ exercises.	3.80	VSA	3.73	VSA
3. enhance understanding of content.	3.93	VSA	3.73	VSA
4. aim to develop learners' critical awareness, linguistic empowerment and learner autonomy.	3.93	VSA	3.87	VSA
5. are based on universal topics, which are culturally specific but they are present in all cultures.	3.93	VSA	3.67	VSA
	Mean	3.87 VSA	3.73	VSA
	Overall Average	3.80		VSA

Legend: *M* (Mean); *VI* (Verbal Interpretation); 3.26-4.00 VSA (Very Strongly Agree); 2.51-3.25 (Strongly Agree); 1.76-2.50 (Agree); 1.00-1.75 (Disagree)

The findings imply that the processing tasks/questions are presented at a pace that allows reflection and review, adequately provide supplementary activities/exercises, enhance understanding of content, aim to develop learners' critical awareness, linguistic empowerment and learner autonomy, and are based on universal topics, which are culturally specific but are present in all cultures.

Johnson (2020) claims that good modules include knowledge consumption through essential skills such as reading, listening and viewing. These provide opportunities for students to process the concept they have learned. This processing can be in the form of a quiz, application activity, discussions or reflections. Instructors often expect learners to demonstrate their acquired knowledge or skills in different forms of assessments.

Assessment Tasks. Table 6 shows the evaluation of the course instructors and the expert respondents on the developed Purposive Communication course module in terms of the assessment tasks to evaluate how student communicative skills and understanding of the concepts are measured.

Table 6. *Evaluation on the Developed Oral Communication Course Module in terms of Assessment Tasks*

<i>Assessment Tasks</i> <i>The assessment tasks...</i>	<i>Instructors</i>		<i>Experts</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. help increase understanding and retention of the content covered.	3.93	VSA	3.80	VSA
2. focus on important objectives and content of the lessons showing congruence.	3.87	VSA	3.80	VSA
3. measure higher order thinking skills.	3.93	VSA	3.87	VSA
4. are clear and are written at a level that students can understand.	3.93	VSA	3.80	VSA
5. enable the students to identify important concepts of communication/language researches.	3.93	VSA	3.80	VSA
	Mean	3.92 VSA	3.81	VSA
	Overall Average	3.87		VSA

Legend: *M* (Mean); *VI* (Verbal Interpretation); 3.26-4.00 VSA (Very Strongly Agree); 2.51-3.25 (Strongly Agree); 1.76-2.50 (Agree); 1.00-1.75 (Disagree)

As presented in Table 6, the evaluation of the developed course module in terms of the lesson content were evaluated by instructors with a mean of 3.92 with a verbal interpretation of Very Strongly Agree (VSA), and by experts with a mean of 3.81 with a verbal interpretation of Very Strongly Agree (VSA), which resulted to an overall average mean of 3.87 with verbal interpretation of Very Strongly Agree (VSA).

The data imply that the developed course module is very highly acceptable in terms of the assessment tasks. This means that the assessment tasks help increase understanding and retention of the content covered, focus on the important objectives and content of the

lessons showing congruence, measure higher order thinking skills, are clear and are written at a level that students can understand and enable the students to identify important concepts of communication or language researches.

Mikell (2020) suggested that each module should include the course content, topics, assignments and tasks, resources and appropriate assessment focused on themes and level of learners. For modular activities, Mikell suggests that each module can begin with a checklist of items for completion inclusive of due dates. They should also be aligned to its measurable learning objectives, with resources and activities, organized and easy-to-follow, clear and concise directions and applicable assessments aligned to the objectives.

Table 7 shows the summary of the respondents' evaluation on the developed course module in terms of course learning outcomes, lesson content, processing tasks/questions and assessment tasks.

Table 7 presents values that correspond to the evaluation of the two groups of respondents. Through the quantitative values, it can be inferred the developed Purposive Communication course module is highly acceptable as grand mean values reveal a Very Strongly Agree (VSA) verbal interpretation from instructors and expert respondents with grand mean ratings of 3.92 and 3.81, respectively, resulting to an overall grand mean of 3.86 which is verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree (VSA).

Table 7. Summary of the Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed Purposive Communication Course Module

Criteria	Instructors		Experts	
	M	VI	M	VI
1. Course Learning Outcomes	3.93	VSA	3.80	VSA
2. Lesson Content	3.87	VSA	3.80	VSA
3. Processing Questions/Tasks	3.93	VSA	3.87	VSA
4. Assessment Tasks	3.93	VSA	3.80	VSA
Grand Mean	3.92	VSA	3.81	VSA
Overall Grand Mean	3.86		VSA	

Legend: M (Mean); VI (Verbal Interpretation); 3.26-4.00 VSA (Very Strongly Agree); 2.51-3.25 (Strongly Agree); 1.76-2.50 (Agree); 1.00-1.75 (Disagree)

The data shows that the developed course module is very highly acceptable in terms the course learning outcomes, lesson content, processing questions/tasks and assessment tasks because of the aforementioned reasons in the individual criterion interpretation. This implies that the parts of the course module namely course learning outcomes, lesson content, processing tasks/questions and assessment tasks have met their standards, opinions, and requirements on how to develop a Purposive Communication module based on the course syllabus aligned with CMO No. 20 s 2013 curriculum guide.

Test of Significant Difference on the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Purposive Communication Course Module for Freshmen College Students

Tables 8 to 11 present the test of significant difference on the evaluation of the instructor and expert respondents on the developed Purposive Communication course module for freshmen college students in terms of course learning outcomes, lesson content, processing tasks/questions and assessment tasks. Table 12 presents the summary on the test of significance on the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the developed course module.

Course Learning Outcomes. Table 8 shows the test of significant difference on the evaluation of the course instructors and the expert respondents on the developed Purposive Communication course module in terms of the course learning outcomes.

Table 8. Test of Significant Difference on the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Purposive Communication Course Module in Terms of the Course Learning Outcomes

Course Learning Outcomes	M	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Instructors	3.91	0.05	Failed to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Experts	3.65			

Note: Significant at $p < 0.05$

As shown in Table 8, since the computed p-value of 0.05 is not less than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is confirmed. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluation of instructors and experts on the developed course module in terms of the course learning outcomes.

The data revealed that both instructors and experts have the same opinions that the Course Learning Outcomes of the developed course module are measurable, attainable and aligned with CHED standards.

Lesson Content. Table 9 shows the test of significant difference on the evaluation of the course instructors and the expert respondents on the developed Purposive Communication course module in terms of the lesson content.

As shown in Table 9, since the computed p-value of 0.14 is not less than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is confirmed. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluation of instructors and experts on the developed course module in terms

of the lesson content.

Table 9. *Test of Significant Difference on the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Purposive Communication Course Module in Terms of the Lesson Content*

<i>Lesson Content</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Instructors	3.91	0.14	Failed to reject the Ho	Not Significant
Experts	3.73			

Note: Significant at $p < 0.05$

The data revealed that both instructors and experts have the same views that in terms of the lesson content, the developed Purposive Communication course module introduces the most important aspects, has well-expressed ideas, concepts and points which lead to the attainment of course objectives, and illustrate current, accurate and defensible examples.

Processing Tasks/Questions. Table 10 shows the test of significant difference on the evaluation of the course instructors and the expert respondents on the developed Purposive Communication course module in terms of the lesson content.

Table 10. *Test of Significant Difference on the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Purposive Communication Course Module in Terms of the Processing Tasks/Questions*

<i>Processing Tasks/Questions</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Instructors	3.87	0.20	Failed to reject the Ho	Not Significant
Experts	3.73			

Note: Significant at $p < 0.05$

As shown in Table 10, since the computed p-value of 0.20 is not less than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is confirmed. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluation of instructors and experts on the developed course module in terms of the processing tasks/questions.

This shows that both instructors and experts have the same views that the developed Purposive Communication module has tasks and questions that are presented at a pace that allows reflection and review, aim to develop learners' critical awareness, linguistic empowerment and learner autonomy, and are based on universal topics.

Assessment Tasks. Table 11 shows the test of significant difference on the evaluation of the course instructors and the expert respondents on the developed Purposive Communication course module in terms of the assessment tasks.

Table 11. *Test of Significant Difference on the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Purposive Communication Course Module in Terms of the Assessment Tasks*

<i>Assessment Tasks</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Instructors	3.92	0.29	Failed to reject the Ho	Not Significant
Experts	3.81			

Note: Significant at $p < 0.05$

As shown in Table 11, since the computed p-value of 0.29 is not less than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is confirmed. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluation of instructors and experts on the developed course module in terms of the assessment tasks.

The data revealed that both instructors and experts agree that in terms of assessment tasks, the developed Purposive Communication course module helps increase understanding and retention of the content covered, focuses on the important objectives and content of the lessons, measures higher order thinking skills, is clear and written at a level that students understand and enables students to identify important concepts of communication and language researches.

Table 12 summarizes the tests of significant difference between the evaluation of the instructor and expert respondents on the developed Purposive Communication course module. Data confirmed that the p-values of 0.05, 0.14, 0.20 and 0.29 for the course learning outcomes, lesson content, processing tasks/questions and assessment tasks, respectively, are not less than the 5% level of significance, thereby showing that there is no significant difference the evaluation of the two groups of respondents in terms of course learning outcomes, lesson content, processing tasks/questions and assessment tasks of the develop Purposive Communication course module. Furthermore the results failed to reject the null hypothesis as it states that there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents.

Since the differences shown are not statistically significant, the data implies that the instructors and expert respondents agree that the developed course module is very acceptable in terms of the course learning outcomes, lesson content, processing tasks/questions and assessment tasks.

Table 12. *Summary on the Test of Significant Difference on the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents in Purposive Communication Course Module*

<i>Criterion</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Course Learning Outcomes	0.05	Failed to reject the Ho	Not Significant
Lesson Content	0.14	Failed to reject the Ho	Not Significant
Processing Tasks/Questions	0.20	Failed to reject the Ho	Not Significant
Assessment Tasks	0.29	Failed to reject the Ho	Not Significant

Conclusions

Comments and Suggestions of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Purposive Communication Course Module Freshmen College Students

Instructors' comments include everything is good, timely and relevant for the class as it requires critical thinking with a possible concern is how other students may find some sample case studies alienating, given that some are time/culture/context-specific. (Ex. BBM, Leni); the module will definitely help NU be more efficient, excellent and useful; the module is reflective of what are needed in a course material for Purposive Communication; the Course Learning Outcomes (CLOs) per lesson are clearly stated, discussions and activities are congruent to the CLOs, examples and illustrations are generously provided, serving as ample guides to learners, processing tasks and assessment tasks observe the SMART criteria. Instructions are clear and specific; rubrics are well-written, providing learners with a vivid picture of what are expected from them and their output; and, references are duly listed.

Some comments about the developed Purposive Communication course module include being exemplary to curriculum builders, excellent, useful, reflective and easy to understand. Course Learning Outcomes (CLOs) are clearly stated, discussions and activities are congruent to CLOs, the processing tasks and assessment tasks have clear instructions and well-written rubrics, and the references are duly listed.

The following statements present the comments of the expert respondents on the developed Purposive Communication course module: the Purposive Communication objectives and lessons are very much effective and aligned with the CMO; the module is a better reference book for college students and instructors; the module is easy to follow, free of grammatical errors, and aligned with the learning outcomes; and the topics are organized, and the tasks are appropriate.

These data reveals positive feedback coming from the instructor respondents in terms of the course learning outcomes, lesson content, processing tasks/questions and assessment tasks.

In response to a comment that there is a possibility that some sample case studies are alienating because they are time/culture/content-specific. Time/culture/context-specific examples can be replaced or adjusted if it will not be relevant to the specific timeline. The specific task (BBM and Leni official campaign video from YouTube) aimed to identify the target audience through electoral campaigns, and the instructor has the freedom to choose a material appropriate for the current culture. However, historical records such as these will still remain relevant as time goes by.

Furthermore, comments confirm that the Purposive Communication course module has received positive feedback coming from the expert respondents and has satisfied their standards on how to craft a Purposive Communication course module for freshmen college students.

The following presents the suggestions of the instructors to further improve the developed Purposive Communication course module for freshmen college students: make the module more appealing to the eyes of the students, give examples that will help them understand the topic; the module may utilize additional supplementary activities/exercises which learners can do independently to further apply the knowledge and practice the skills they have learned; and add or enhance some parts with regards to culture in order to see the purpose of communication.

The following are the suggestions of experts on how to improve the developed Purposive Communication course module for freshmen students: provide small activities yet interactive to activate the engagement of students that logically lead to the abstraction of the lesson and before the assessment of each chapter that might be achieved through giving a 10-item objective type test; expose the learners with different designs of research regarding communication; presentation materials and examples can be more diverse in subject since the course emphasizes cultural competence since most, if not all examples are only in the Philippine context and should also be reiterated in all lessons and in the final project.

Experts suggested providing small and interactive activities for student engagement before the assessment of each chapter. In addition, objective-type assessment tasks are also encouraged on top of the analytic tasks. Moreover, it is also suggested to expose learners into different designs with regard to communication researches and additional international cultural diversity to move out from only Philippine context.

Suggestions on making the module more visually appealing aim enhance student understanding. In addition, supplementary activities or exercises for student independent practice are also recommended and more content that deals with culture to strengthen the purpose

of communication. The data implies that the physical features of the module are important for the respondents to engage the learners and the supplementary activities are necessary to prompt the learners in applying communication concepts. Furthermore, their exposure to diverse cultures must also be increased, making them delve more on the concepts of sociolinguistics.

These useful suggestions from the respondents can further improve the module because they recommend learners to be more interactive in terms of activities, exercises and assessments through supplementing additional parts such as objective-type assessments, encouraging familiarization of the concepts. The suggestions also imply that multiculturalism is of utmost importance since it is the essence of being communicatively competent, and the exposure to different research designs will also widen the knowledge of students in empirical investigation so that one day they can effectively investigate and provide solutions to problems in their respective fields through research. These suggestions will not just make students learn important concepts in research but will also make them become more engaged on important issues that need to be addressed locally and internationally.

Insights

Curriculum development is an essential step towards more inclusive classroom learning and teaching strategies. In the world of communication, the language evolves together with cultural and generational changes. Hence, 21st century learners shall be facilitated through learning materials in the way that would be relevant to them, both academically and culturally. This would fulfill the objectives set by the Purposive Communication curriculum. The study offered a number of insights.

A course module in Purposive Communication for freshmen students and for a trimester set-up can be developed based on the course syllabus in reference to the CHED Memorandum Order No. 20 s. 2013 curriculum guide. The developed Purposive Communication course module for freshmen students in NU Fairview is very acceptable in terms of course learning outcomes, lesson content, processing task/questions and assessment tasks. There are comments and suggestions from instructors and experts in order to improve the developed Purposive Communication course module.

Therefore, the guidance of instructors and experts would be significant in developing learning materials. Furthermore, the Purposive Communication course module is recommended to be used in General Education classes as a supplementary module for instructors and as guidance of students towards a more meaningful teaching-learning process for research-based language and communication classes. Moreover, further studies should be done to determine the effectiveness of the Purposive Communication Course Module for Freshmen Students.

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